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THE IMPORTANCE OF A GLOBAL STANDARD OF GOOD AGRICULTURE PROGRAM (G.A.P) FOR THE PRODUCTION AND EXPORT OF ORGANIC PRODUCTS IN AGRICULTURE IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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ANNOTATION

The article aims to improve the production of organic and environmentally pure environmentally friendly products in the production of quality food in the country's agriculture and the supply of the population. Proposals and recommendations are also made to further improve the introduction of international standards of the International Global Good Agriculture Program (G.A.P) in the export of organic and environmentally friendly products.

Key words: environmental products, organic products, import-export, international standards, Global Good Agriculture Program (G.A.P).

INTRODUCTION

It is important that Uzbekistan enters the world market and becomes a member of international trade organizations. Therefore, as a result of the intensification of Export-import Operations as a result of the integration of our country into international trade, today it is pouring the requirements for the provision of the world's population with quality and safe food products.

As a result of the implementation of important measures by the state in the field of growing organic products in agriculture and ensuring the quality and safety of food, our republic is a global Good Agriculture Program (G.A.P), which includes requirements for the quality and safety of food, the conditions for its production, preparation, procurement, processing, supply, storage, transportation and export. there are problems with the introduction of international quality standards.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In our country, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-5995 "On additional measures to ensure the compliance of quality and safety indicators of agricultural products with international standards" of May 18, 2020 and the analysis of the effectiveness of reforms in the field of Plant Quarantine of our President Shavkat Mirziyoev on September 21, 2020, issues of bringing.

Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 18, 2020 "On additional measures to ensure the compliance of quality and safety indicators of agricultural products with international standards" PF-5995 directly affects the growth of exports in our country on the basis of increasing the volume of organic products.

Today, according to the analysis of the International Institute of organic agricultural research, 172 of the world's more than 250 countries are engaged in organic agricultural cultivation. More than 90 countries have regulatory acts in the field of organic agriculture. For the cultivation of organic agricultural products, 2.3 million farms have been found to be occupied on 43.7 million hectares of land worldwide.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

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Today, organic agriculture is a world trend. In 2019, the trade turnover in international markets for organic agriculture was 96.7 billion. the euro amounted to 71.5 million. 2.8 million producers on an area of hectares were engaged in this type of activity.

The global organic products market has seen an average growth of 15% per annum over the past 5 years, with a trade turnover of 212 crore in 2022. The U.S. dollar (20% of the total world agricultural production) was projected to be.

Indeed, according to the Institute for organic agricultural research (FiBL), 103 countries around the world have adopted an organic agriculture law, with 6 countries developing a law.

The 2019 edition of the Institute for organic agricultural research (FiBL) and the International Federation for organic agricultural movement (IFOAM) on World Organic Agricultural Statistics lists the Republic of Uzbekistan among 10 countries in the world with favorable conditions for fruit production and notes that the Republic has favorable land areas for organic fruit production.

The increasing quality and safety requirements imposed on products in the world market require additional measures to strengthen the position of products grown in our republic in international markets.

The development of production, regulation and coordination systems in accordance with the requirements of the international standards of Organic and Global Good Agriculture Programm (G.A.P), improvement of quality and safety indicators of rural and forestry products, expansion of export geography, as well as increasing the possibility of full use of the organic product production potential of our country.

As stipulated by the decree, the development of production, regulation and coordination systems in accordance with the requirements of the international standards of Organic and Global Good Agriculture Programm (G.A.P) in our republic, improving quality and safety indicators of their products, expanding export geography, and also further increasing the possibility of full use of the organic product production potential of our country. In order to ensure the implementation of the decree, a program with a specific address was established by the agency "technical regulation". According to it, the implementation of global Good Agriculture Programm (G.A.P) in 155 enterprises and farms and organic international standards in 9 enterprises during the current year is established.

Today, 90 businesses and farms have included a package of documents pertaining to the Export Promotion Agency in an effort to cover costs associated with the introduction of the Global (G.A.P) and organic standards. In the cross section, the Global Good Agriculture Programm (G.A.P.) at enterprises established to implement the standard, address work is organized, and work in this direction is continued in 57 enterprises and farms.

CONCLUSION

Manufacturers in more than 124 countries around the world are certified by the GLOBAL (G.A.P) system, the total number of farms with this certificate exceeds 170,000. According to available data, the share of crop products (including fruits and vegetables) from the total number of certified farms is about 75%, the share of livestock products is 15%, and the share of aquaekins is 10%. In increasing the role of global (G.A.P) international quality standards in the production and export of organic products, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

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- wide introduction of Global (G.A.P) international quality standards in the formation and export of organic products in our country;
- it is in the cultivation of agricultural products that organic products increase the yield;
- to ensure timely formation of contracts related to the cultivation of organic products in agriculture, as well as to ensure the fulfillment of the terms of the contract;
- it is necessary to achieve a reliable partner in World Trade by supplying export products to agricultural enterprises on the basis of the broad introduction of international quality standards of Global (G.A.P).

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